

THE ROLE OF COUNSELING PSYCHOLOGY IN THE SYSTEM OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASSISTANCE

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Abstract. *Counseling psychology and psychocorrection reflect the specifics of providing psychological counseling or advice to clients and organizing corrective practices in the psychologist's practice. The practical process of interaction between a practicing psychologist and a client is based on psychological counseling or psychocorrection. The brief definition of the term "psychological counseling and psychocorrection" is the interaction between a psychologist, therapist, or consultant and a client.*

Keywords: *psychological service, psychological assistance, consultation, training, therapy, psychodiagnostics, psychocorrection, problem, tension, stress, consultant, client, appeal.*

Introduction. The origins of providing psychological assistance to people date back to ancient times. Although there were no psychologists in those days, priests, religious figures, and philosophers carried out such duties. While religious scholars did not employ specific psychological methods to offer spiritual support, they reflected elements of these methods in their activities. In other words, they listened to people's problems and offered comfort. The establishment of psychological services performed specifically by specialists—namely, psychologists—dates back to the early 19th century. In particular, psychological services began to develop in the United States in the 1800s. The first practicing psychologists in the U.S. were experimental psychologists who studied the problem of self-education.

The main purpose of psychological counseling and psychocorrection is to assist clients with problems related to cognitive disorders, emotional strain, or behavioral difficulties. To help clients, a psychologist applies knowledge from personality theory as well as the principles of psychocorrection or counseling. The psychologist's approach to assisting clients must be based on legal and ethical foundations. There are various perspectives on how to distinguish between psychological counseling and psychocorrection. Some scholars believe that counseling is applied to individuals with a normal psychological state, whereas psychocorrection is used for those experiencing severe stress. The main challenge lies in differentiating the intensity of stress, as practicing psychologists sometimes use the same techniques for varying levels of tension. Another distinction is that counseling aims at teaching and providing information, while correction focuses on alleviating the problem.

From this, it can be concluded that counseling involves giving advice based on personality theories, while correction requires active practical involvement toward the client. Psychological counseling is an important branch of applied psychology, which involves providing psychological advice and assistance to individuals in need by a professional psychologist. This process takes place through conversations focused on exploring the client's problem. The word *consultation* derives from the Latin *consultare*, meaning "to give advice" or "to take care." Therefore, the Uzbek term *maslahat* (advice) can be considered synonymous with it.

The emergence of counseling psychology as a science dates back to the mid-twentieth century. This process is directly associated with James Bugental's publication of *The Art of the Psychotherapist* in the West in 1987. The book was later published in Russia in 2001. Counseling psychology is a branch of applied psychology that was established to provide psychological assistance to individuals who do not have clinical deviations. H. Burkus and B. Steffire (1979) defined the process of psychological counseling as follows: "Counseling is a professional relationship between a patient and a psychologist."

A single session of psychological counseling may last from several dozen minutes to one and a half or even two hours. During the session, the client speaks about their problem, while the psychologist listens attentively and attempts to uncover its core. In the process of giving advice, the psychologist takes into account the client's personal characteristics and provides scientifically grounded recommendations aimed at finding a comprehensive solution to the problem. Psychological counseling aims to help individuals develop confidence in taking responsibility for solving the problematic situations that arise in their lives. This process represents a highly responsible task for the counselor because the client may not fully understand the root cause of their problem or know how to resolve it.

Since 1994, research institutions around the world have begun to study the problem of Internet addiction in the field of education. Today, this issue has become one of the "trendy topics" in scientific psychology, and many studies are devoted to it. Special attention is given to examining the influence of Internet addiction on the development of individuals' psychological, social, cultural, and moral qualities, particularly among students. From the perspective of age characteristics, adolescence can be described as a period of self-control, when a person's behavior, as well as anxiety about future plans, becomes especially significant.

Object of the Research and Methods Used.

The object of the research is psychological counseling, particularly sources related to counseling practice involving clients. In addressing the topic, descriptive, comparative, contextual, complex, and functional analysis methods were employed.

Findings and Their Analysis.

A counselor's meetings with a client do not usually end after one or two sessions; they may continue for three or even more sessions. The duration of counseling depends on several factors:

1. The complexity of the problem—when multiple issues intertwine and create new ones, it takes more time to identify the essence of the problem and provide appropriate advice.
2. The recommendation given may require adjustment to suit the client's personal characteristics, necessitating additional sessions.
3. The client's internal problems may manifest externally,
4. making it difficult to identify the core of the issue and requiring further investigation.

Typically, individuals who have difficulty adapting to life or are physically or psychologically weak seek psychological counseling. Additionally, those who consider themselves unsuccessful or find it hard to achieve success in life often turn to psychologists. Such people are often characterized by feelings of insecurity about their future, pessimism, and emotional coldness. A psychologist, through scientific understanding, identifies the basis of these mental states and provides appropriate psychological guidance to help clients overcome them.

Clients usually seek counseling for the following reasons:

1. The client knows how to solve their problem but lacks self-confidence and therefore turns to a psychologist.
2. The client does not know how to solve the problem and seeks advice on how to proceed.
3. The client feels uncertain or hesitant about possible solutions and needs help choosing the right path.
4. The client wishes to have an open, confidential conversation with a psychologist about their problems and emotional experiences.

The Main Functions of Psychological Counseling

1. **Identifying the problem faced by the client.** This process involves listening to the client carefully and making an accurate conclusion about the essence of their problem.
2. **Informing the client about the nature and seriousness of the problem.** At this stage, the psychologist clearly explains the root cause of the problem and how it emerged, providing evidence-based explanations. The counselor also outlines possible ways to solve the issue.
3. **Studying the client's personality** to determine whether they can independently solve their problem. Without this process, it is impossible for the client to fully understand their issue or take an active role in resolving it. By examining the client's personality, the psychologist can explain the problem while taking into account the client's individual characteristics.
4. **Formulating clear and practical recommendations** for effectively solving the problem. Knowing both the root cause of the issue and the client's personal traits, the psychologist provides optimal and realistic advice. Such guidance should be concise, simple, easy to understand, and applicable in real life.
5. **Providing ongoing practical support** in the form of additional advice. The client may not be able to implement the psychologist's initial recommendations immediately, so additional sessions and practical advice are often required.
6. **Performing a psycho-preventive function**, that is, teaching the client how to prevent similar problems in the future. Since psychologically based issues tend to recur in life, the psychologist provides preventive advice to minimize the likelihood of similar problems arising again.
7. **Teaching clients essential psychological knowledge and skills** that are necessary for solving problems independently. Acquiring such skills helps clients handle difficulties more effectively on their own.

The main purpose of psychological counseling is to help the client improve their psycho-emotional state, understand their problems, enhance relationships with others, and improve their overall quality of life. The means to achieve these goals include various psychotherapeutic methods such as active listening, helping the client understand the problem and find ways to resolve it, as well as providing information and psychological support.

The Main Objectives of Counseling:

- **To relieve emotional tension** and eliminate discomfort caused by stress, crises, or other life difficulties.
- **To develop self-awareness** and understanding of one's problems—recognizing the causes and mechanisms of psychological reactions and identifying the reasons behind certain behaviors.
- **To enhance psychological competence** by forming new, positive ways of perceiving oneself and one's problems.

- **To develop adaptability**, increase stress resistance, and strengthen one's ability to cope with external influences.
- **To improve interpersonal relationships** through better communication and conflict resolution skills.
- **To increase responsibility**, helping the client recognize their role in solving problems and take accountability for their actions and choices.

Today, various types of psychological problems are identified. Of course, these problems are primarily related to a person's mental and emotional state. Therefore, in psychological practice, counseling is organized to address the following psychological issues:

Men and Women:

1. Infidelity and jealousy
2. Emotional dependence on a close person
3. Love triangles
4. Having a partner with unpleasant behavior
5. General issues in interpersonal relationships
6. Psychological trauma and loss
7. Death and grief
8. Parent–child relationship problems
9. Issues related to sexual activity
10. Problems of adolescents and teenagers
11. Personality-related issues
12. Fear and anxiety
13. Depression
14. Loneliness (social isolation, unfulfilled personal happiness)
15. Finding one's place in life
16. Psychological problems of loved ones
17. Problems in the educational process
18. Career and marketing-related issues
19. Professional counseling (problems related to career choice)

Conclusion. The process of psychological counseling does not require an in-depth application of psychodiagnostics. This process is carried out by analyzing and generalizing the information obtained directly from the client, without the use of special psychological tests. In providing psychological assistance to a client, in addition to counseling, the practice of psychocorrection is also used. While psychological counseling is a short-term process in the form of advice provided by the psychologist, the psychocorrection process is long-term and requires the psychologist to be actively involved in implementing certain behavioral or emotional changes. The psychologist should strive to create an environment in which the client views the resolution of their problems with optimism. The directions of psychological schools that have a practical basis are applied in a general and harmonious way in both psychological counseling and psychocorrection practices. The psychocorrection process primarily requires studying and evaluating the client based on psychodiagnostics.

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